

ML2++ in Practice: A Model-Driven Engineering Workflow for IoT ML and Time-Series Forecasting

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Abstract: ML2++ is a model-driven framework that extends ThingML to integrate data analytics, machine learning (ML), and time-series forecasting into IoT system design. Building on the ML2 and ML2+ domain-specific modeling languages, ML2++ provides a dual modeling environment with a textual editor (Textula) and a graphical editor (Sirius-Web). In these editors, users declaratively specify data sources, preprocessing steps, ML and forecasting algorithms, evaluation criteria, and visualization settings, all without manual coding. In addition to presenting the complete workflow, this tutorial paper also reports results from a usability evaluation involving both the Textula editor and the Sirius-Web graphical environment. The study assesses ease of use, modeling effort, and interaction patterns across both DSLs. We present an end-to-end workflow that combines Textula and Sirius-Web with a web-based Orchestrator, covering model authoring, code generation, execution, visualization, and evaluation for IoT-based predictive and analytics workflows. The tutorial enables IoT engineers, data scientists, and MDE researchers to design forecasting-enabled IoT systems, automatically generate executable Python/Java projects, and interpret resulting metrics and visual outputs in a reproducible way.

1 Introduction

Machine learning (ML) and time-series forecasting are increasingly central to modern Internet of Things (IoT) applications, enabling intelligent monitoring, predictive maintenance, and decision support (Alulema et al., 2020). However, developing and maintaining ML-enabled IoT systems typically requires substantial manual coding and coordination across heterogeneous tools and technologies. This fragmentation harms reproducibility and raises the entry barrier for domain experts. Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) addresses these challenges by raising the level of abstraction at which systems are specified. Domain-Specific Modeling Languages (DSMLs) capture analytical workflows as high-level models from which executable code can be automatically generated (Korani et al., 2025a; Korani et al., 2025b;

Moin et al., 2022). The ML2 family of DSMLs (ML2, ML2+, and ML2++) was developed to bridge MDE and ML by providing declarative constructs for complete ML and time-series forecasting pipelines. ML2++ (Korani et al., 2025b) extends this family with automated visualization, multi-algorithm support, and dual editing environments: a textual editor (Textula) and a graphical editor (Sirius-Web). Both editors generate consistent Python/Java artifacts for preprocessing, training, forecasting, and visualization. A broader technical account of the underlying metamodel and architecture appears in (Korani et al., 2025b), while related approaches for MDE and ML in IoT are discussed in (Moin et al., 2022). Before developing this tutorial, we conducted a literature review and comparative analysis to position ML2++ within the landscape of existing tools (Korani et al., 2025b). As shown in that study, widely used plat-

forms such as TensorFlow/Keras, KNIME, RapidMiner, and PMML provide robust ML or visualization capabilities, yet they do not support seamless model-to-code generation, unified ML–forecasting pipelines, or integrated interpretability. In contrast, MDE-based tools such as ThingML or micro-Kevoore automate IoT system modeling but lack built-in analytics and visualization capabilities. ML2++ was therefore designed as a comprehensive and extensible framework that combines DSML-driven automation, dual-mode modeling, and integrated visualization within a single environment. In addition to presenting the modeling workflow, this tutorial paper includes a small-scale usability evaluation of both ML2 (textual DSL) and ML2++ (graphical DSL). Participants constructed complete IoT–ML models using Textula and Sirius-Web, configured DAML analytics pipelines, executed real forecasting workflows, and provided structured feedback. This evaluation offers empirical insight into ease of use, modeling effort, DAML configuration complexity, and user interaction patterns. These findings complement the technical contributions of ML2++ by validating its practical usability in realistic scenarios. Building on our two previous ML2++ papers (Korani et al., 2025a; Korani et al., 2025b), this tutorial paper focuses on practical usage rather than on metamodel and architectural details. The earlier publications (i) introduced the ML2 / ML2+ / ML2++ family of DSMLs and their metamodels, (ii) described the overall architecture and code generation pipeline, and (iii) positioned ML2++ among related MDE and ML tools for IoT. In contrast, the present paper is explicitly tutorial-oriented and targets practitioners who want to apply ML2++ in concrete IoT scenarios. More specifically, this work makes three tutorial-specific contributions. First, we present the first complete, step-by-step workflow that integrates the textual editor (Textula), the graphical editor (Sirius-Web), and the Orchestrator into a unified modeling–execution pipeline. Second, we structure ML2++ usage into clear phases (IoT system modeling, data-analytics specification, graphical configuration, and execution), with concrete modeling steps and screenshots that attendees can follow during and after the tutorial. Third, we describe and provide access to the web-based editors, Docker configurations, and example repositories that participants can use to reproduce the tutorial and adapt it to their own datasets. Table 1 summarizes how this tutorial paper complements and extends earlier ML2++ publications. The remainder of the paper is structured to mirror this flow. Section 2 introduces ML2++, its architecture, the Textula editor, and the main steps to define the IoT messaging and configuration, specify

Table 1: Scope of previous ML2++ papers vs. this tutorial paper.

	Prior ML2 / ML2+ / ML2++ papers	This tutorial paper
Focus	Metamodels, architecture, model families, and conceptual integration of MDE and ML/TSF	Practical usage, dual editor workflow, step-by-step modeling and execution
Content	Formal description of DSML constructs; architectural diagrams; comparative analysis with related tools	Hands-on instructions; concrete IoT case study; screenshots and example models
Artifacts	Prototype implementation, code generators, and early case studies	Tutorial projects, Dockerized Orchestrator setup.

data_analytics blocks for ML and forecasting, and execute and visualize the results. Section 2.3 demonstrates the graphical workflow with Sirius-Web and the Orchestrator, including model creation, DAML forms, project execution. Section 3 presents the usability evaluation and summarizes the key findings. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future work.

1.1 Tutorial Audience and Learning Objectives

This tutorial is aimed at three main audiences: (i) IoT engineers who want to incorporate ML and time-series forecasting into their systems without extensive Python programming, (ii) data scientists who are interested in Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) and domain-specific modeling languages, and (iii) MDE researchers who wish to explore concrete tooling for analytics-intensive IoT applications. By the end of the tutorial, participants will be able to:

- Model an IoT system with sensors, analytics components, and dashboards using ML2++ in both textual (Textula) and graphical (Sirius-Web) environments.
- Specify complete data analytics and time-series forecasting pipelines (data sources, preprocessing, model configuration, evaluation, and visualization) using the data_analytics construct.
- Generate executable Python/Java projects from models and run them through the Orchestrator to inspect training, forecasting, and diagnostic plots.
- Understand the trade-offs between textual and graphical modeling and how ML2++ can be integrated into existing IoT engineering workflows.

2 Overview of ML2++

ML2++ brings together Model-Driven Engineering (MDE), machine learning (ML), time-series forecasting (TSF), and automated visualization to let practitioners describe end-to-end analytics and forecasting

workflows for IoT systems with minimal glue code. Users may work in the textual environment (*Textula*) or the graphical environment (*Sirius-Web*); both target the same metamodel and can produce equivalent artifacts for preprocessing, model training, multi-step TSF, evaluation, and visualization (Korani et al., 2025b).

2.1 Architecture

ML2++ follows a three-layer architecture that connects modeling, code generation, and execution/visualization:

- **Modeling layer.** Users specify analytics and forecasting workflows using *Textula* (textual DSL) or *Sirius-Web* (graphical canvas with form-based modeling). Both act as front-ends on a shared metamodel and cover data specification, preprocessing choices, temporal framing (lags, horizons, multivariate TSF), model selection, evaluation, and visualization.
- **Code generation layer.** Xtend-based compilers translate abstract models into runnable Python/Java projects, generating preprocessing pipelines, training routines, multi-horizon forecasting logic, and visualization assets directly from the `data_analytics` blocks. Xtend-based compilers translate abstract models into runnable Python/Java projects, generating preprocessing pipelines, training routines, multi-horizon forecasting logic, and visualization assets directly from the `data_analytics` blocks.
- **Execution & visualization layer.** Generated projects may be executed locally or via the web-based Orchestrator, which automates workflow execution and produces diagnostic outputs such as training-loss curves, forecast vs. actual plots (single and multi-step), residual analyses, and feature-correlation heatmaps.

2.2 Textual Editor

The **Textula editor**¹ is the browser-based textual environment of ML2++. It lets users define IoT systems and their analytics/forecasting workflows in a unified DSL, with syntax highlighting, real-time validation, and one-click code generation for preprocessing, training, forecasting, and visualization, without requiring programming expertise.

In the current prototype, the Textula page is organized as a workspace with a single text editor on the

left, an empty area for future extensions on the right, and a console output panel at the bottom. Below the editor, a row of action buttons guides users through the end-to-end workflow. The overall layout of this workspace is illustrated in Fig. 1.

- **Save Model** – Persists the current ML2++ specification on the server. It performs a quick syntactic check and reports parsing or validation errors in the console but does not generate or execute any artefacts yet.
- **Show Preprocessing Plot** – Triggers only the data loading and preprocessing logic defined in the `data_analytics` block (e.g., alignment, resampling, handling missing values). It then renders a preview plot so the user can visually inspect data quality before training.
- **Generate Code** – Translates the ML2++ model into executable Python and Java artefacts for preprocessing, training, forecasting, and visualization. The generated scripts are stored on the server, and compilation logs appear in the console panel.
- **Download Code** – Packages all generated artefacts (scripts, configuration files, and helper modules) into a downloadable archive, enabling offline execution or integration into CI/CD pipelines.
- **Run Code** – Executes the generated workflow on the server. This includes preprocessing, model training (or loading a saved model), and multi-step forecasting. Structured logs are streamed to the console in real time.
- **Show Forecasting Plots** – Displays the latest evaluation artefacts, such as forecasting curves, comparison between predictions and ground truth, multi-step horizons, and overfitting diagnostics. This action does not re-run the model but only visualizes stored results.

Together, these buttons provide a fully automated, no-code execution cycle, allowing users to iterate rapidly on their ML2++ specifications entirely within the browser.

A Textula model integrates two complementary elements:

1. **IoT system specification** (ThingML-like): messages, ports, and configurations that interconnect sensors, analytics, and actuators.
2. A **data_analytics** block: the complete ML2++ pipeline (data ingestion, preprocessing, model training, time-series forecasting, evaluation, and visualization).

¹<https://ml2plusplus.jvmhost.net/login.html>

Figure 1: ML2++ Textula workspace showing the model editor, console output, and plot gallery.

2.2.1 Step 1 — Defining Messages, Ports, and Configuration

Before introducing analytics logic, the first step in ML2++ is to model the communication layer of the system. This layer specifies how data flows between sensors, analytics modules, dashboards, controllers, and any external user interfaces or actuators. Defining this layer is essential because all later stages of preprocessing, training, prediction, and visualization depend on well-specified message types and port interactions.

Messages. Messages are strongly typed data packets exchanged among components. Each message declares a name and a list of fields with explicit types, which ensures type-safety, analyzability, and deterministic communication semantics across the system. Listing 1 illustrates a set of abstract message declara-

tions. These include: (i) an *ingestion* message carrying raw sensor observations, (ii) a *prediction* message carrying model outputs and timestamps, (iii) a *control* message encoding actuator commands, and (iv) an *acknowledgment* message used for confirming successful processing. All ML2++ models begin with such message definitions because they form the contract governing all interactions in the deployed architecture.

Listing 1: Abstract message declarations.

```

1 message <IngestMsg>(<t1> <f1>, <t2> <f2>, ...)
2 message <PredictMsg>(<tp> <y_hat>, <t>
   <timestamp>, ...)
3 message <ControlMsg>(<tc> <command>, <t>
   <target>, ...)
4 message <AckMsg>(<tb> <ok>, <t> <info>)

```

Ports and Things. A Thing is the fundamental behavioral unit in ML2++/ThingML. It encapsulates state, internal variables, and communication ports. Ports specify which messages the Thing may send or receive, thereby defining its external interface. In ML2++, a Thing may also embed a `data_analytics` block, transforming the component into an analytics-enabled node capable of performing preprocessing, training, inference, and visualization directly at runtime. This constitutes a major extension over standard ThingML and enables hybrid IoT+ML workflows to be modeled concisely. Listing 2 shows an example Thing that receives ingestion messages, stores them as internal features, and transitions to a prediction state. In the `<Predicting>` state, the analytics backend computes one or more predictions and emits a `<PredictMsg>` back through the same port. The example demonstrates the tight integration between communication and analytics logic in ML2++, enabling seamless end-to-end dataflow.

Listing 2: Port bindings and embedded analytics in a Thing.

```

1 thing <AnalyticsThing> {
2   port <AnalyticsPort> { receives <IngestMsg>,
   sends <PredictMsg> }
3   property <prop_name> : <Type> = <default>
4
5   data_analytics <da_id> @dalib "<backend>" { ...
   }
6
7   state <Ready> {
8     on <IngestMsg> from <AnalyticsPort> ->
   <Predicting> { }
9   }
10  state <Predicting> {
11    entry { send <PredictMsg>(<y_hat>,
   <timestamp>) to <AnalyticsPort> }
12    -> <Ready>

```

```

13 }
14   init <Ready>
15 }

```

Configuration. The configuration section instantiates the system and wires its components into a working deployment architecture. Each instance corresponds to a concrete runtime component, while connect statements specify directed communication channels between ports. Listing 3 shows a typical configuration in which: (i) a sensor component forwards measurements to an analytics module, and (ii) the analytics module forwards its predictions to a dashboard or UI Thing. This structural layer finalizes the executable topology of the application: it defines who talks to whom, what messages flow through each connector, and how the IoT and ML components interact during operation.

Listing 3: Configuration wiring for sensors, analytics, and dashboards.

```

1 configuration <SystemConfig> {
2   instance <SensorA>      : <SensorThing>
3   instance <Analyzer>    : <AnalyticsThing>
4   instance <Dashboard>  : <UiThing>
5
6   connect <SensorA>.<SensePort>      =>
7     <Analyzer>.<AnalyticsPort>
8   connect <Analyzer>.<AnalyticsPort> =>
9     <Dashboard>.<UiPort>
10 }

```

Together, Listings 1, 2, and 3 define the communication substrate of an ML2++ system. This substrate provides the foundation on which preprocessing, learning, forecasting, and control logic are later constructed.

For quick reference, Table 2 provides a compact overview of the main ThingML syntax commands used to define Things, ports, messages, statecharts, connectors, and data-analytics triggers in ML2++ models.

2.2.2 Step 2 — Defining data_analytics Blocks

Each block declaratively describes a complete pipeline from raw data to plotted results that support time-series forecasting, regression, classification, clustering, and anomaly detection.

Grammar overview. The `data_analytics` block comprises six modular sections `data`, `preprocessing`, `time_series`, `model`, `evaluation`, and `visualization`. In the tutorial we use only a core subset of these directives; the remaining options are available in the online documentation:

Listing 4: ML2++ Textula grammar for a `data_analytics` block.

```

1 data_analytics <id> @dalib "<backend>" {
2   // e.g., "keras-tf", "python"
3   data {
4     dataset "<path|source>";
5     // CSV file or IoT stream
6     features <x1>, <x2>, ...;
7     output_features <y1>[, <y2>, ...];
8     [timestamps ON|OFF];
9     // default: ON if timestamp exists
10    [common_period_threshold <int>];
11    // e.g., 10
12  }
13  preprocessing {
14    [fill_missing OFF|MEAN|FF|BF|INTERPOLATION];
15    [scaler OFF|Standard|MinMax|Robust];
16    [normalizer OFF|L1|L2|MAX];
17    [remove_outliers OFF|ON];
18    [resample
19      MINUTELY|HOURLY|DAILY|WEEKLY|MONTHLY|YEARLY];
20    [transform LOG|DIFF|STANDARDIZE|NORMALIZE|
21      SMOOTH|AGGREGATE|UPSAMPLE|DOWNSAMPLE];
22  }
23  time_series {
24    [sequential TRUE|FALSE];
25    // default: TRUE
26    [steps <k>];
27    // forecast horizon (multi-step)
28    [lag <p>];
29    // look-back window
30    [multivariate ON|OFF];
31    // default: ON if > 1 feature
32    [stationarity_check ON|OFF];
33    [seasonality FOURIER|MOVING_AVERAGE|OFF];
34    [supervised TRUE|FALSE];
35    [sliding_window ON|OFF];
36    // default: ON if lag > 1
37  }
38  model {
39    [autoML ON|OFF];
40    algorithm <ALG>([params]);
41    // e.g., LSTM(neurons 64, epochs 100)
42    [tuning OFF|GRID|RANDOM|BAYESIAN];
43    [ensemble OFF|BAGGING|BOOSTING|STACKING];
44    [blackbox TRUE|FALSE];
45    [blackbox_model "<.pk1|.h5>"];
46    [blackbox_algorithm "<Name>"];
47    [label_encoder "<le.pk1>"];
48  }
49  evaluation {
50    [prediction_results <p1>[, <p2>, ...]];
51    [metrics RMSE|MAE|MSE|R_SQUARED];
52    [outlier_detection ON|OFF];
53    [clustering ON|OFF];
54    [context
55      "RiverFlow|ServerMonitoring|IoT|Other"];
56  }
57  visualization {
58    [plots
59      LINE_PLOT|BOX_PLOT|HEATMAP|ACF|CORR_MATRIX|
60      TRAINING_LOSS|VALIDATION_LOSS|LEARNING_CURVE]
61  }
62 }

```

Table 2: ThingML Syntax Commands

Command/Keyword	Purpose	Example
thing	Declare a Thing/component	thing PingClient { ... }
thing fragment	Declare reusable message fragment	thing fragment PingPongMsgs { message ping(ip: String); }
message	Define message	message ping(ip: String);
provided port	Declare provided port	provided port ping_service { receives ping sends pong }
required port	Declare required port	required port ping_service { sends ping receives pong }
property	Declare internal variable	property my_ip_address: String = "192.168.1.1"
statechart	Define state machine	statechart Behavior init Idle { ... }
state	Declare state	state Ping { on entry do ... end }
on entry do ... end	Actions on entering a state	on entry do ping_service!ping(my_ip_address) end
transition → State	Transition to another state	transition -> Pong
transition → State event port?msg	Transition on message event	transition -> Pong event ping_service?pong
transition → State event port?msg	Transition on message event	transition -> Pong event ping_service?pong
internal event e: port?msg	Capture incoming message	internal event e: ping_service?ping
action do ... end	Execute multiple actions	action do client_ip_address = e.ip end
if (cond) ... else ...	Conditional execution	if (prediction == 0) da_service!prediction_negative() else da_service!prediction_positive()
stop	Stop state machine	stop
connector	Connect ports	connector pingClient.ping_service => pingServer.ping_service
instance	Instantiate a Thing	instance pingClient : PingClient
da_preprocess	Trigger preprocessing	on entry do da_preprocess da1 end
da_train	Trigger training	on entry do da_train da1 end
da_predict	Trigger prediction	on entry do da_predict da1(client_ip_address) end
da_save	Save model state	on exit do da_save da1 end

```

48 FORECAST_VS_ACTUAL | FORECAST_ERROR |
49 FORECAST_INTERVALS | RESIDUALS |
50 CONFUSION_MATRIX | ROC_CURVE | PR_CURVE];
51 }
52 }

```

Each section of the data block `_analytics` corresponds to a distinct stage in the end-to-end machine-learning lifecycle that covers data acquisition, preprocessing, temporal structuring, model construction, evaluation, and visualization and together define a complete declarative pipeline that ML2++ can automatically generate and execute.

- **data:** datasets, features/targets, and temporal structure.

- **preprocessing:** cleaning, scaling/normalizing, re-sampling, and transforms.
- **time series:** lag, horizon, multivariate, seasonality, supervision.
- **model:** algorithm choice (e.g., LSTM, GRU, XGBoost), AutoML/tuning/ensembles, black-box models. Table 3 summarizes the families and backends of the algorithms.
- **evaluation:** metrics and optional analyses.
- **visualization:** automatic plots for diagnostics and interpretability.

The editor validates this structure and supports sequential flow *preprocessing* → *training* → *prediction*

Table 3: Supported models and corresponding libraries in ML2++.

Category	Models / Algorithms	Backend / Library
Deep Learning	LSTM, GRU, RNN, CNN, MLP, TCN, Transformer	Keras, TensorFlow
Statistical	ARIMA, SARIMA, HWES, ETS, State-Space Models	statsmodels, pmdarima
ML (Classical)	SVR, RFR, GBM, XGBoost	scikit-learn, xgboost
Hybrid / Probabilistic	ARIMA-GARCH, Prophet	Prophet
ML2 Core	Linear/Logistic Reg., Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, K-Means, DBSCAN, Spectral Clust., Gaussian Mixture, Self-Training, Label Prop.	scikit-learn

→ *visualization*, enabling reproducible, model-driven analytics pipelines in the same specification that defines the IoT architecture.

2.2.3 Step 3 — Execution and Visualization

After code generation, the Orchestrator (or local runtime) executes the generated Python/Java project and automatically produces all visual outputs. These include preprocessing plots that summarize data quality and temporal structure, prediction and forecasting plots that highlight model behavior and errors, and training/overfitting plots that show loss and convergence patterns. Table ?? lists the full set of plot types supported by ML2++.

2.3 Graphical Modeling with Sirius-Web and the Orchestrator

This section presents the graphical workflow of ML2++ with Sirius-Web and Orchestrator. While Textula focuses on textual modeling, Sirius-Web offers a canvas-based editor and form views that are convenient for users who prefer visual modeling. Both front-ends share the same metamodel, so models created in Textula and Sirius-Web are conceptually equivalent and lead to the same generated Python/Java projects. At a high level, the graphical workflow consists of three steps: (i) open or upload the ML2++ project in Sirius-Web, (ii) create and edit an instance model using the canvas and forms, and (iii) generate and execute the corresponding analytics project with the Orchestrator.

2.3.1 Setting up Sirius-Web and the Orchestrator

Sirius-Web and the Orchestrator are distributed together in the ML2++ graphical repository and can be launched locally using Docker. Listing 5 shows the

Figure 2: Sirius-Web homepage and Project Overview interface.

Figure 3: Sirius-Web editor layout showing Model Explorer, canvas, and Form View.

commands required to clone the repository, build the containers, and start both components.

Listing 5: Launching the ML2++ Orchestrator and Sirius-Web locally.

```
1 git clone https://github.com/ThimotyS/ML-plusplus
2 docker-compose build
3 docker-compose up
```

After deployment, the Orchestrator runs at <http://localhost:8081> and Sirius-Web at <http://localhost:8083>. The Sirius-Web homepage (Fig. 2) provides the project overview screen, and the editor interface (Fig. 3) exposes the model explorer, canvas, and form views. For this tutorial, a ready-made ML2++ project archive is provided; participants can upload it directly using the Upload Project command, which creates a new workspace entry without additional configuration.

2.3.2 Creating a Model Instance in Sirius-Web

Once the project is loaded, users create an ML2++ instance model that mirrors the structure of the running example (e.g., sensors, analytics component, and dashboard). The Sirius-Web interface exposes three main panels:

1. the *Model Explorer*, which shows the instance hierarchy;
2. the *graphical canvas*, which displays the elements and their connections;

Figure 4: Creating a new model by first creating the Domain in the Model Explorer.

Figure 6: Root object (ThingMLModel) creation dialog.

Figure 5: Using the tree view to add a root object to the Domain.

Figure 7: Invoking the object creation wizard via New Object.

3. the *Form View*, which exposes the attributes of the selected element.

Starting from a root `ThingMLModel` object (Figure 4), the user creates Things, ports, messages, and properties using the contextual menus in the model explorer or directly from the canvas (Figures 5–14). New graphical representations are created via the *New representation* command, which opens an empty canvas (Figures 9 and 11). Elements can then be added and connected using right-click menus (Figures 12–16), while their names, types, and default values are edited in the Form View (Figures 17 and 18). In the tutorial, we instantiate a small configuration corresponding to the smart-home or river-flow scenario: a sensor Thing that produces measurements, an analytics Thing with an attached `data_analytics` block, and a dashboard Thing that receives predictions. The same pattern can be reused for other IoT applications by changing the dataset and analytics configuration.

2.3.3 Configuring Data Analytics and Models via Forms

Data analytics and ML configurations are edited through dedicated multi-page forms. When a `data_analytics` element is selected, Sirius-Web displays a DAML form with tabs for data set, preprocessing, time-series settings, evaluation and visual-

Figure 8: Selecting the element type from the drop-down menu.

Figure 9: Creating a new graphical representation for the model.

ization (Figure 19). Selecting a concrete ML algorithm (e.g., Linear Regression, Random Forest,

Figure 10: Choosing the view type and title for the representation.

Figure 11: Empty canvas after creating a new representation.

Figure 12: Right-click context menu on the canvas for model manipulation.

LSTM) opens a model-specific page where the user can configure hyperparameters such as the number of estimators, hidden units, epochs, or batch size (Figure 19). These graphical forms mirror the structure of the `data_analytics` block used in Textula, ensuring that the same pipeline can be specified either textually

(c) Sub-menu for different actions

Figure 13: Submenu with creation, connection, and layout actions.

Figure 14: Object displayed on the canvas after creation.

Figure 15: Object-specific menu for the selected element, or graphically.

2.3.4 Executing Models with the Orchestrator

The Orchestrator takes the instance model produced in Sirius-Web and generates an executable ML2++ project. After logging into the web interface (Figure 20), the user selects the project, triggers code generation, and optionally uploads the dataset associated with the `data_analytics` block (Figure 21). The Orchestrator then runs the generated Python/Java

Figure 16: Creating a link between objects to represent a relationship.

db_service

Core Properties

Name

db_service

Sends

serverStatus Values

Receives

Values

Optional

Figure 17: Form View for a Port element (bindings and direction).

AS_cpu_user

Core Properties

Name

AS_cpu_user

Readonly

Figure 18: Form View for a Property element (name, type, default).

code, producing plots and reports such as preprocessing summaries, training curves, and forecast-versus-actual visualizations. Generated files, images, and logs can be inspected directly in the browser or downloaded for offline analysis.

3 Evaluation

This section reports the results of our usability evaluation, which examined both ML2 (textual DSL) and ML2++ (graphical DSL). Importantly, the evaluation of ML2++ also covers the full interaction experience

NewDataAnalytics Form

Data Preprocessing Time Series Model Evaluation Visualisation Model Algorithm

Dataset

data/appserver01_data_string.csv

Features

DA_cpu_user DA_cpu_system DA_cpu_util DA_disk_read DA_disk_write DA_mem_used DA_swap_used DA_net_eth0_tx DA_net_eth0_rx DA_net_eth1_tx DA_net_eth1_rx DA_sch_threads DA_app_status Values

Input Features

Values

Output Features

Values

Labels ON NOT_SET OFF ON SEMI

Timestamps OFF NOT_SET OFF ON

Common Period Threshold

0

Figure 19: DAML configuration page with data, preprocessing, and time-series parameters

Projects

Upload a new Project

Project Overview

Original File Name	Date	Import	Reupload	Details
Cargo.xml	25.07.2020	Import	Reupload	Details

Figure 20: Orchestrator: generation and execution of an ML2++ project.

stress.xml

Generate Project Delete All Delete Dataset

Update Project Update Dataset

File Type	File Name	Status
Original	stress.xml	Generated
Converted	stress.daml	Generated
Thought	generated stress thought	Generated
Thought Project	generated stress	Generated
Dataset	stress.xml.csv	Uploaded

Project Output

Execute Project Download Images Download Output Download Report

Generated Output
Generated Project
Generated Report

Figure 21: Orchestrator: generated files, images, and reports panels.

with the Sirius-Web graphical editor, including its model explorer, canvas, and form-based configuration views. Participants interacted with the editor to create Things, connect ports, configure DAML blocks, and execute model-driven analytics workflows.

3.1 Participants and Use-Case Setup

Eight participants completed the usability study after screening from the initial invited group. To ensure balanced comparison conditions, they were divided into two groups according to educational level, technical background, and self-rated experience in IoT/CPS, MDE, and ML/Data Science: *Group A* worked with the textual DSL (ML-Quadrat/ML2), while *Group B* used the graphical DSL (ML2++). Both groups showed comparable academic and professional experience, including basic familiarity with IoT and ML. Participants completed three progres-

sively complex scenarios—stress-level classification, soil-moisture regression, and server-failure prediction—each requiring the design of Things, messages, ports, properties, behaviors, and a DAML configuration. ML-Quadrat users were provided with a corrected version supporting all promised DAML features, while ML2++ users worked either with a pre-configured environment or a Docker deployment.

3.2 Ease of Use: Summary of Findings

The ease-of-use results, summarized in Figure 22w, show that both DSLs performed similarly for basic constructs such as fragments, messages, and Thing properties. ML2++ demonstrated improvements for defining data types, objects, and Things, owing to its graphical layout and preconfigured model elements. The most substantial gains were observed in port specification, configuration wiring, and especially the DAML section, where ML2 required strict keyword ordering and imposed higher cognitive load. In contrast, ML2++ offered form-based parameter entry with visual guidance, which participants consistently rated easier. Behaviour modeling remained equally challenging in both DSLs due to the need to write executable state logic. Overall, ML2++ significantly reduced cognitive effort for structural modeling and ML configuration, as illustrated by the aggregated usability results in Figure 22w.

4 Conclusion

This tutorial presented ML2++, a unified framework for modeling, executing, and visualizing IoT and machine-learning workflows. By integrating ThingML-style IoT abstractions with declarative data analytics, automated code generation, and built-in visualization capabilities, ML2++ addresses the fragmented and error-prone toolchains commonly used in IoT-ML development. The Textula editor enables rapid, textual modeling with real-time validation and one-click execution, while the Sirius-Web graphical environment offers a complementary low-code interface with form-based DAML configuration and guided system construction. Together with the Orchestrator, ML2++ provides a complete pipeline from high-level specifications to executable Python/Java artefacts for preprocessing, training, forecasting, and evaluation. We also conducted a small-scale usability evaluation involving both Textula and Sirius-Web editors. The results indicate that participants found ML2++ intuitive, particularly in tasks involving ports, configuration, and DAML setup. The form-

driven interface of Sirius-Web and the automated analytics pipeline significantly reduced cognitive load compared to traditional DSL-based modeling. Feedback from participants further validated the design decisions of ML2++ and highlighted several directions for refinement, such as improving behavior modeling support and enhancing reuse mechanisms across use cases.

Future work will focus on extending ML2++ with additional ML algorithms, richer visualization libraries, automated hyperparameter tuning, and support for online/real-time data ingestion. We also aim to broaden the evaluation with a larger participant sample and more diverse use cases to assess scalability and generalizability. Ultimately, ML2++ aspires to become a comprehensive, accessible, and extensible platform for developing intelligent IoT systems with integrated analytics and forecasting.

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(w) Ease-of-use ratings for (a) ML2 (textual DSL) and (b) ML2++ (graphical DSL / Sirius-Web) across DSL constructs (top rows) and ML pipeline steps (bottom rows).